

RES4CITY CASE STUDY #9

Sustainable Bioenergy and Side bio-products Production on coastal urban areas

By Halmstad University

What is biogas?

Biogas is an eco-friendly energy source produced from decomposing organic materials like manure, food waste, and agricultural residues. It reduces methane emissions and provides a renewable alternative to fossil fuels. Used for generating heat, electricity, and vehicle fuel, biogas helps lower carbon footprints and supports sustainable energy practices.

The Swedish case study

- ✓ **Vessige Biogas:** A cooperative of about 30 members, including large animal farms, produces biogas from manure and other substrates. The biogas is used for heating, electricity, and vehicle fuel. Government support has been vital to its development, aiding rural growth and climate goals.
- ✓ **Sotenäs Symbiocenter:** Established in 2011, this network connects maritime industry actors with a privately owned biogas plant (Renahav). It facilitates resource exchanges between sea and land, using biogas from industrial by-products. The center is expanding to boost resource use in the food industry, agriculture, and aquaculture.

Benefits of industrial symbiosis

Industrial symbiosis is a collaboration where one company's waste becomes another's resource, leading to improved efficiency and reduced environmental impact. **This approach not only maximizes resource use but also fosters local economic growth by creating job opportunities and promoting sustainability in various industries.**

Some challenges lie ahead

Biogas production faces challenges such as low profitability and fragmented stakeholder coordination. To address these issues, the study suggests creating regional strategies, enhancing communication among businesses, and learning from successful examples. Overcoming these barriers requires proactive facilitation and supportive policies to boost biogas use.

Future directions

To accelerate the adoption of biogas, it's essential to build strong networks among stakeholders and invest in infrastructure. Encouraging continuous learning, sharing knowledge, and implementing effective collaboration models will be key to expanding biogas production and its role in a greener, more sustainable future.

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Stay tuned & follow us for more insights!

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